

Why

Research Design

matters

Maria Machado

What's Research Design?

Methodology utilized to answer research questions.

**Defines
research
question.**


```
graph TD; A[Defines research question.] --> B[Outlines the theories and models underlying a project.]; B --> C[Strategy for gathering data and its analysis.]; C --> D[Produces answers that are valid, reliable, precise, and relevant.];
```

**Outlines the theories and
models underlying a project.**

**Strategy for gathering data
and its analysis.**

**Produces answers that are
valid, reliable, precise, and relevant.**

Design Principles

- **Unit of study:** *the smallest object that could be randomly and independently assigned to an intervention.*
- **Blocking:** *precision in the estimation of the source of variation.*
- **Variables:** *dependent and independent.*

Design Principles

- **Sampling:** *convenience or systematic.*
- **Measurement:** *use of metrology standards.*
- **Uncertainty:** *determination of sample size.*
- **Comparison:** *to a control.*
- **Randomization:** *to mitigate confounding.*
- **Masking:** *to reduce operator bias.*

Design is determinant for:

- 1. Planning:** minimization of bias, sample size determination, and statistical analyses.
- 2. Conducting the study:** recording all important information.
- 3. Writing up the manuscript:** used as an aide memoire to include all relevant information.
- 4. Reviewing the manuscript:** to enable the evaluation of the research.

**Would you like to know what a
sound research design looks like?**

DM me for actionable feedback.

Maria Machado